

The degree of practice of servant leadership among secondary school principals in Haifa District in the Palestinian interior and its relationship to the level of motivation of teachers

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Abstract: This study aimed to reveal the extent to which secondary school principals in Haifa District in the Palestinian interior practice servant leadership and its relationship to the level of motivation of teachers, and the correlational descriptive approach was used. The study relied on two questionnaires in data collection, the first for the degree to which secondary school principals practice servant leadership, and the second for the level of teacher's motivation. The study population consisted of all secondary school teachers in Haifa District in the Palestinian interior, numbering (3287) teachers, and the study sample consisted of (410) teachers, and the results showed that the degree of practice of secondary school principals in Haifa District in the Palestinian interior for the altruistic dimension has come in the first rank and with a high degree of evaluation, followed by loved dimension and has a high degree of evaluation, followed by humility dimension and has come with a high degree of appreciation, while the results showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the dimensions of servant leadership due to the variables of gender, experience, and scientific qualification, and the results showed that the level of motivation among teachers came at a high level in all Items, and there were statistically significant differences due to the gender variable and the differences came in favor of females. The results also showed a positive correlation between servant leadership among principals and motivation among teachers.

Keywords: Servant leadership, Motivation, High schools, Haifa District.

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Introduction

Leadership is the essence and focus of the administrative process, it is necessary for all organizations regardless of the type of activity they practice, and in all administrative processes of planning, organizing, motivating, controlling and making decisions, and directs and coordinates the processes of action and reaction according to the surrounding circumstances, it is affected and influential by the environment in which it operates, and it is the heart of the other administrative process, and it is one of the most important elements that developing and developed societies suffer from lack alike (Daldol, 2016).

The leader has a great task in directing the efforts of employees towards achieving goals through his ability to influence their behavior, and make administrative work more effective and dynamic, able to influence employees, their motives and goals to be consistent with the goals of the organization, and to have the characteristics of creativity, change and adaptation to the internal and external environment by focusing on the central role of all, and

working to raise the level of the workers to achievement, and development of employees and organizations, and attention to skills, commitment and transparency and Communication (Laila, 2015).

With the development of managerial thought in the twenty-first century, modern trends in management theory, such as ethical, participatory and servant management, have emerged to replace traditional theories such as trait theory and the great man theory. These modern leadership styles are characterized by the leader's high ability to face various modern changes and developments, by influencing the behavior of employees and developing their capabilities and potentials, and pushing their enthusiasm to do their work voluntarily without using official authority, and solving their problems in scientific and systematic ways, which helps in raising the productivity and development of institutions. It achieves its strategic and future goals and plans (Fullan, 2014).

The servant leader looks at followers as partners rather than subordinates, and understands their needs and empathizes with

them, beyond self-care to altruism and care for his subordinates (Spears, 2010).

The idea of servant leadership is based on the principle of service first for workers to later provide service to others, unlike the school of human relations and the behavioral school of providing reward and service as a later stage after the workers have implemented what is required of them (Gandolfi. & Stone, 2018).

The importance of servant leadership is highlighted in that it satisfies the needs of educational institutions, and servant leadership enhances organizational confidence among employees and empowers them, encourages the spirit of creativity, innovation and initiative, promotes positive behavior among employees, and increases servant leadership in the participation of employees in the decision-making process. It gives them the powers and responsibility that carry out the work (Stewart, 2017).

The importance of servant leadership in the educational field lies in raising the morale and motivation of teachers, due to their effective contributions to achieving a high level of participation, and forming second rows of leaders, to be more effective and independent through their inspiration of satisfaction and dedication to serving their students (Kamal, 2019).

The first axis: the general framework of the study

Study problem

Many previous studies such as Al-Abadela (2022), Al-Anezi (2021), Al-Daihani (2017), Irnidayanti, Maulana, Lorenz & Fadhilah (2020), and Al-Naser (2018) have confirmed the importance of servant leadership and motivation among teachers in schools and the need to pay attention to the practice of service leadership by secondary school principals because of its impact on teachers' motivation to accomplish in their work, loyalty and organizational commitment. Due to the lack of studies that dealt with the practice of servant leadership and its relationship to achievement motivation among teachers in secondary schools in the Palestinian interior, so the problem of the study is to identify the degree of practice of secondary school principals in Haifa District in the Palestinian interior of servant leadership and its relationship to the motivation of teachers.

Study Questions

- 1- What is the degree to which the principals of secondary schools in Haifa District in the Palestinian interior practice servant leadership from the teachers' point of view?
- 2- Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the average response of the study sample of teachers on the degree of practice of servant leadership among secondary school principals in Haifa District in the Palestinian interior due to the different variables of gender, experience and qualification?
- 3- What is the level of motivation of secondary school teachers in Haifa District in the Palestinian interior?
- 4- Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the average response of the study sample members in the level of motivation of secondary school teachers in Haifa District due to the variables of gender, experience and educational qualification?

- 5- Is there a statistically significant correlation at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the servant leadership of secondary school principals and the level of motivation of secondary school teachers in Haifa district?

Objectives of the study

- 1- A statement of the degree of practice of the principals of secondary schools in Haifa District in the Palestinian interior of servant leadership.
- 2- Identify the level of motivation of secondary school teachers in Haifa district.
- 3- Revealing the type and degree of relationship between servant leadership among secondary school principals and motivation among teachers in Haifa District.

The importance of the study

This study derives its importance from the importance of its subject, which deals with important variables in the administrative field, as servant leadership is one of the modern trends in leadership, and motivation among teachers is one of the important topics in the field of organizational behavior, which helps to know the behavior of individuals in educational institutions, and more specifically it is hoped from the results of this study that:

- Contributes to revealing the relationship between the servant leadership of the school principal and the motivation of secondary school teachers in Haifa District in the Palestinian interior.
- This study may contribute to the educational field by providing an encouraging environment for servant leadership in educational institutions.
- The results of this study can help enhance the motivation of teachers, which positively affects the achievement of job satisfaction, organizational commitment, contributing to achieving the goals of the educational institution, improving performance, and increasing organizational loyalty among teachers.

Method and procedure

The methodology and procedures of the study are a major axis through which the applied side of the study was accomplished, and through it the data required to conduct statistical analysis were obtained to reach the results that were interpreted in the light of the literature of studies related to the subject of the study.

Study Methodology

The study adopted the correlational descriptive approach to answer the questions of the study, due to its appropriateness and the nature of this study and its objectives.

Population and sample of the study

The study population consisted of all secondary school teachers in Haifa District in the Palestinian interior for the academic year 2022/2023, which numbered (3287), and a random sample of (410) teachers was selected from the study population, and the following table shows this:

Table 1: Distribution of study sample members

Variables	Categories	Iteration	Percentage
Sex	male	213	52
	female	197	48
Experience	Less than 5 years	54	13.1
	5-10 years	107	26
	10 years and above	249	60.9
Qualification	Bachelor	235	57.3
	Master and above	165	42.7
	Total	410	100.0

Study Tools

The study questionnaire was developed to collect data by referring to the theoretical literature and previous studies related to the study problem, such as the study of Abadela (2022), study Al-Anzi (2021), and the study Al-Masri & Farah (2020), and Al-Naser study (2018), and conducting an exploratory study to find out the most important areas that must be included in the questionnaire, and the questionnaire included paragraphs measuring the degree of practice of leadership dimensions The servant leadership by high school principals in Haifa District In the Palestinian interior, consisting of (20) items distributed over four dimensions:

First dimension: altruism (5) items.

Second dimension: empowerment (5) items.

Third dimension: loved (5) items.

Fourth dimension: humility (5) items.

The second questionnaire measures the level of motivation of secondary school teachers in Haifa district, consisting of (18) items.

To facilitate the interpretation of the results, the responses in each axis were distributed according to the Likert pentameter as follows: very high = 5, high = 4, medium = 3, low = 2, very low = 1

The closed questionnaire has been adopted in the preparation of questionnaires, which determines the possible responses to each question, and the answers have been classified into five categories of equal range through the following equation:

To determine the criterion for judging the score, **namely: Class length = (highest value in scale scale – lowest value) divided by the number of options in the scale (5).**

$$\text{Class length} = (5-1) \div 5 = 0.8$$

Category	Averages	Degree of approval
The first	4.21 – 5	Very high
The second	3.41 – 4.20	High
Third	2.61 – 3.40	Medium
Fourth	1.81 – 2.60	Low
Fifth	1.00 – 1.80	Very low

Servant Leadership

The style of servant leadership was formulated by Greenleaf when he published his classic article "Leader-as Servant" published in 1977. It has been found that many people suffer from the term "leader-servant" and some interested people believed that he could not be a servant and a leader at the same time, because they are two different and contradictory things that cannot be logically combined. This is confirmed by Kamal (2019) When she pointed out that the idea of servant leadership is contradictory and cannot be compromised, if the servant is complimentary and flattering, and that the leader is strong and in control, then those words will indeed seem contradictory and cannot be combined.

The concept of servant leadership

The School of Human Relations and then the Behavioral School worked to address the conflict between management on a culture of profit and loss and not on profit and profit. That is, leadership provides reward and service to workers as a later stage after the workers have implemented what they have to do, and have proven that they are under the influence of leadership, but in servant leadership, you are required to serve first, and then you can drive easily and smoothly expressed by the workers themselves with a strong desire to serve others (Dugan & Aslan. 2016).

Servant leadership described as humanitarian principles and has characteristics and practices that focus on the fundamental principles of equality, respect and integrity in the organization and society. Al-Juhani (2019) defines it as the understanding and practice of leadership that transcends the attention or self-interests of the leader, and this leadership promotes the valuation and development of people, community building, fairness with love for others, and giving leadership to the fittest people to lead and share influence and status for the benefit of all members of the organization and the organization itself, as well as those it serves.

Basic characteristics of Server Commander

Spears (2010) classified ten servant-leader qualities that he saw as central and critical to server leader development:

- 1- Listening: the servant leader must know the needs and will of the group to serve them. So he should listen to what is being said, taking regular periods of reflection on what is being said.
- 2- Empathy: the servant leader must empathize with the needs of the team after he understands them. He must assume goodwill in

his collaborators, even if he sometimes has to refuse their level of performance.

3- Healing: one of the greatest strengths of servant leadership is growth in healing oneself and healing others. That is, helping those who deal with them in times of crisis and adversity.

4- Awareness: general awareness of the surrounding matters, and self-awareness raises the level of the servant leader. In order for a servant leader to remain open to situations, he must have a strong sense of personal awareness and self-acceptance, which gives him inner calm and tranquility, which serves as a light for external awareness, learning, and continuity of service with a willingness to accept difficult truths.

5- Persuasion: it is the ability of the servant leader to convince others to take actions that enhance their growth and self-development, and the servant leader can encourage workers to make decisions and actions towards the right directions.

6- Vision: vision drives the performance of the team as the servant leader is the agent of the organization.

7- Insight: it is the characteristic that allows the servant leader to be aware of the lessons learned from the past, the reality of the present and the expected future results of making a decision.

8- Supervision: the leader believes that his role is to preserve the wealth and resources of the institution, and use them for the benefit of society.

9. Commitment to the advancement of Others: the servant leader is convinced that people have real value beyond their contributions as followers, and should therefore nurture the growth of the personal, professional, and spiritual aspects of followers.

10- Building a cohesive society: the ability to grow and develop the human race in society is a characteristic of a servant leader as well as fighting selfishness and creating opportunities for others to work in small groups that are all the backbone of society.

Dimensions of servant driving

A group of researchers adopted seven dimensions of servant leadership (Stewart, 2017):

1- Conceptual skills: possess knowledge about the organization and the tasks assigned to him so that he is in a position to enable the leader to provide effective assistance and support and facilitate the tasks of others, especially direct subordinates.

2- Empowerment: encouraging and providing facilities to others, especially direct subordinates, by identifying and solving problems, as well as determining when and how to complete work tasks to the fullest.

3- Helping subordinates develop and succeed: provide real attention to the growth of subordinates by providing the necessary support and guidance.

4- Paying attention to subordinates first: using the clear to others, meeting their work needs and considering it a priority.

5- Acting ethically: dealing openly, honestly and fairly with others.

6- Emotional processing: show interest in the personal interests of others.

7- Commitment to community development: real awareness towards developing and helping society.

The importance of servant leadership

Servant leadership works to accommodate internal and external variables and adapt them for the benefit of the institution, and encourages teamwork, which increases and develops productivity, and attaches great importance to human resources as it seeks to empower school staff and encourage them to continuously learn, grow and be independent.

The shift towards servant leadership moves the school from the traditional hierarchical style of leadership to a new model based on team and group, and the importance is evident in the fact that servant leadership is able to absorb the rapid changes in the current era, where the most competition and constant concern due to technological and demographic changes and the strength of international competition (Baldonado, 2017).

Coetzer, Bussin & Geldenhuys (2017) stated that servant leadership seems more important through the role of servant leader who appears from transcending his personal interests and caring for serving the needs of others, helping them achieve growth and development and giving them the opportunity to achieve what they aspire to financially and socially and urging them to work together to achieve the goals of the school in which they work.

Gandolfi & Stone (2018) argues that the importance of leadership is shown by the positive results it achieves, which are represented in three axes:

- Organization-wide: promote a higher level of performance under servant leadership that focuses on the needs of people, whether they are affiliated or beneficiaries of the organization.

- At the level of followers: its importance lies in the fact that it cares primarily about followers, achieves their self-esteem, makes them feel independent, appreciates their achievements and efforts, evaluates their work and empathizes with them.

- At the community level: it is evident in the fact that it cares about the human virtues that different societies need.

Benefits of Servant Leadership

Yılmaz & Ceylan (2016) based on Greenleaf summarizes the benefits of servant driving with the following points:

1- Organization development: the servant leader moves from the traditional leadership style that focuses on dominating subordinates and teaching them what to do to the servant leadership style, where it empowers them to work and inspires them, and this inspiration leads to collective efforts, and the results of the work are more and greater than individual efforts.

2- Employee development: servant leadership does not place the goals of the organization on the shoulders of employees, on the contrary, the leader puts effort and time to help subordinates understand their strengths and weaknesses. Such qualities of a leader that most subordinates look for in their leader, lead to job satisfaction and organizational loyalty among employees and help organizations develop and maintain human capital.

3- Team building: servant leadership helps each member of the team to make his contribution based on the skills and experience of each member of the team, and this type of leadership leads to building a team that allows each individual to display his skills and collaborate more effectively with the rest of the team.

4- Achievement: by following the style of servant leadership, the leader engages all team members in setting goals and objectives, each individual has a voice in decision-making, in addition to that the leader creates a positive atmosphere towards their values, and this type of leadership allows employees to set their own key performance indicators. This gives the employee the authority to make changes that lead to the long-term success of the entire organization.

5- Change: servant leadership determines the mission and goals of the organization based on the views of employees, which enables employees to manage their own careers more effectively and achieve the appropriate balance in life when they decide their own future, employees who play an active role in determining the company's transition to a new style of work are more loyal, and more satisfied, which achieves an advantage for the company at the executive level.

6- Satisfaction: when employees work under the leadership of a servant leader, they are actually working collectively and for the benefit of all, and this is reflected in satisfaction rates, because all needs are met. By involving everyone in the decision-making process, the servant leader ensures that everyone's opinions are heard.

7- Community service: community service is one of the first basic principles of servant leadership, as servant leadership contributes to establishing a culture of service to others, whether inside or outside the organization. The importance of servant leadership at the community level is highlighted by the fact that it advocates the human virtues needed by different societies.

Motivation

Each individual has within him a self-drive towards his desires and needs, and this is reflected in his behavior, as this is a motivation for him to accomplish something, and the level of motivation for each individual changes according to his needs and desires, the higher the level of motivation, the higher the level of achievement and performance, so many research and studies have indicated the importance of understanding the internal interactions of individuals working in organizations, which push them to achieve goals, as motivation is an important work in understanding the behavior of individuals.

The concept of motivation

Motivation expresses a set of internal and external conditions that move the individual in order to restore the balance that was disturbed, and according to this concept, motivation refers to the tendency of the individual to push him to reach a specific goal or a certain goal, and this goal may be to satisfy internal needs or desires, while the need refers to a situation that arises in the individual in order to achieve the necessary biological or psychological conditions that lead to maintaining survival and continuity, while the goal is what the individual desires reaching it, while satisfying motivation (Al-Ajami, 2019).

While Irnidayanti, Maulana, Lorenz & Fadhilah, (2020) defines it as a set of forces consisting of a number of internal and external factors that provoke behavior, direct it, determine its intensity and maintain its continuity, and these forces are provoked by multiple factors, which may stem from the individual himself, or from the physical and psychological environment surrounding him.

Mesgouni and Taouriret (2019) believe that motivation represents the individual's ability to achieve work that others see as difficult, control the physical and social environment, control, handle and organize ideas, speed of performance and independence, overcome obstacles, reach standards of excellence, self-superiority, compromise and superiority over others, and self-esteem.

The researcher believes that motivation is the internal causes of behavior, which includes an individual doing a certain action, and determines the direction of that action. Motivation is everything related to those forces that activate human behavior, or maintain it at a certain level, or direct it to a certain destination, and this can be summarized, that motivation is everything related to those forces that maintain or change the direction of the nature and intensity of a behavior.

Types of motivation

Psychologists have classified human motivations into two types: physiological (internal) and acquired (external) motives Ateş and Yilmaz (2018):

1- Physiological motives: they are internal motives that refer to a set of biological needs and instincts that are born with man and do not need to learn, they are known as basic motives or motives for survival because they are necessary in maintaining the survival and continuity of human existence. They are primary innate motives that arise from the body's needs for organic and physiological functions, such as the need for water, food, sex, security and safety, avoidance of danger, and the need for shelter, housing and stability.

2- Acquired motives: they are external motives, as they are acquired or learned through the process of interaction with the physical and social environment according to the processes of reinforcement and punishment provided by society, and these motives use a set of psychological and social needs such as: the need for belonging, friendship, control, appreciation, social acceptance and other motives, such needs develop in individuals through other socialization processes. Simulation plays a prominent role in acquiring such needs and is strengthened according to the implementation process. The reward and punishment that individuals receive from the society in which they live and interact

The importance of motivation

Price (2008, 22) pointed out that everyone wants to be successful, but to be successful they must have motivation towards their work, and listed four reasons why motivation is important:

- Motivation helps the individual to start his work with enthusiasm without having to be forced to work, or tell him how to work.
- Motivation urges the individual to continue his work even if he faces difficulties, this does not hinder the completion of his work, but rather raises a challenge for him.
- Motivation pushes the individual to accomplish more work than is required of him, voluntarily and out of love for his work.
- Motivation makes an individual's work enjoyable and his view of success different, as he always looks forward to reaping the fruits of his success, even if the road is long and full of obstacles.

Based on the above, Zaid (2022) believes that motivation is of great importance in that it works to raise the level of performance

of individuals and their productivity, and this is thus reflected in the economic growth of society in general, and it also makes individuals accept to practice their cognitive, emotional and behavioral activities widely in their daily lives, and this can be exploited educationally by provoking the motivation of individuals towards greater interests and goals to achieve.

Motivation theories

Theories varied and multiplied in the field of motivation, and can be limited to two main types: the first type is content theories, because it allowed to limit the most important motives explaining the behavior of the individual. The second type is practical theories, because it relies on cognitive processes in order to explain how an individual behaves (Al-Obeid and Al-Ruwaili, 2017).

Maslow's ladder theory of needs: this theory is considered one of the most famous theories of motivation, and indicates that human needs are hierarchically arranged in order of importance as follows Sache (2019):

Physiological needs: they are located at the first level and include: food, drink, air, pain avoidance, sex, and other needs that directly serve biological survival.

Safety needs: it includes the needs related to maintaining the needs of physical and moral security, and is represented in the need for a sense of security, stability, order and protection. In the regulatory field, security and protection take the form of job security and ensuring a safe regulatory environment.

Social needs: the human need for a social environment or framework in which a person feels love and harmony, such as the family or society in which he lives, and is referred to as the needs of acceptance and courtship.

Needs of appreciation and respect: self-esteem and a sense of self-worth that emanates from within the individual, the need to gain respect and appreciation from the surrounding environment, the need to gain the respect of others, and also includes good reputation, success and good social status.

Self-realization needs: also known as higher needs, Maslow has placed them at the top of his pyramid, and Maslow has identified a set of higher needs or motives, which the individual reaches after achieving adequate satisfaction of all the needs that preceded at the lower level.

Herzberg's two-factor theory: it is one of the basic theories of job motivation, which says that there are two sets of factors that apply in terms of satisfaction and motivation (Al-Naser, 2018):

The first group: are the driving factors that are related to the content of the job, including interesting work, appreciation, opportunities for career growth and progression, and assuming responsibilities and achievements.

The second group: are the health and basic factors, which if not available, the employee becomes frustrated, but their availability makes him satisfied with his work and becomes motivated when the factors of the first group are achieved. This group includes job stability, appropriate job status, decent workplace, appropriate material income, favorable working conditions, and building social relationships at work.

The theory of the need for achievement for Mclelland: It is the motivation to excel and achievement according to a set of criteria,

and this theory believes that individuals who have a strong need for achievement have the motivation to excel and struggle for success just for success without regard to the financial return, unless it is seen as an indicator of success. This category of people is psychologically interested in getting work done better, developing work, wanting to challenge and do difficult tasks in order to achieve the desired goals. (Price, 2008).

Fromm's Expectations Theory: this theory shows that human behavior is not so simple that it can identify stimuli and experiments that work to satisfy certain needs, but that man conducts a set of mental and thinking processes before it leads to limited behavior.

The theory of expectations is based on four basic concepts mentioned by the Al-Amyan(2018):

The power of desire: it is the individual's belief and awareness that the effort expended in performing a work will lead to the desired achievement. This desire is a result that realizes the expected benefits from performing a particular work.

Expectation: expectation is the belief that doing a certain level of effort puts him in performing a job that deserves a certain level of performance.

Means: it is the way in which a specific result or level can be achieved. (Example: A student may develop a "daily study program of at least two hours" that enables them to obtain a certain result (80 marks and above).

Results: they are what an individual obtains as a result of an effort or performance.

Motivation for achievement

It is the process by which behavior is directed in order to achieve certain goals to satisfy an internal or external need raised, and high motivation is that desire to produce good work and achieve results in tasks with a high degree of excellence and excellence (Mesgouni and Taouririt, 2019).

Among the theories that have emerged in the interpretation of achievement motivation, Atkinson's theory, which is a theory that links the individual's expectation of his performance and his self-awareness of his ability and the consequences thereof, and considers them mutual cognitive relationships that stand behind the behavior of achievement, and that individuals with high motivation for achievement make a great effort in attempts to reach problem solving, and it emphasizes the tendency or tendency to obtain something acquired, can be learned, which varies between individuals, and differs when the individual in different situations, and these motives are affected by three factors The main ones: the motivations to reach success, or the probability of success associated with the difficulty of the task, and the value of success. The high motivation of achievement also increases the ability of individuals to control themselves in hard work to solve the problem, and it enables them to develop solid plans to follow it and follow them up actively to reach a solution (Abdul Rashid and Saidi, 2019).

Al-Masri and Farah (2020) confirm that high-level achievement motivation motivates its members to face and address problems, try to solve them and overcome all the difficulties and obstacles they face. Individuals with achievement motivation are pleased when performing moderate and difficult tasks, and strive with high

energy towards work, in contrast to low-motivation individuals who avoid problems, and quickly agree to solve them when they face difficulties, and it maintains high performance levels for individuals without external control, and this is evidenced by the positive relationship between achievement motivation, perseverance at work and good performance regardless of their mental abilities, and thus achievement motivation is a good way to predict behavior associated with success or failure in Future.

The third axis: Study Results and Discussion

First: Discussing the results related to the first research question, which states: **"What is the degree to which the principals of secondary schools in the Haifa District in the Palestinian interior practice the dimensions of servant leadership?"**

The arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the responses of the study sample members were used to determine the degree of practice of secondary school principals in the Triangle area in the Palestinian interior of the dimensions of servant leadership, and Table (2) illustrates this.

Table 2: Arithmetic Averages and Standard Deviations of the Estimates of the Study Sample Members for the Dimensions of Servant Leadership

No.	Item	Arithmetic Average	Standard Deviation	Rank	Degree
1	Altruism	4.04	0.96	1	High
2	Empowerment	3.78	0.91	4	High
3	Loved	4.00	0.95	2	High
4	modesty	3.87	0.93	3	High
Total		3.92	0.94		High

Table (2) shows that the degree of practice of servant leadership dimensions came with a high degree, the first of which was the altruism dimension (4.04), then the loved dimension (4.00), followed by humility dimension (3.87), and last place the empowerment dimension (3.78). The arithmetic averages ranged between (3.78-4.04). This can be explained by the great role played by the Ministry of Education in developing democratic patterns, including the servant leadership of school principals through rehabilitation programs and training courses dedicated to this field.

The altruism dimension

Table 3: Arithmetic Averages and Standard Deviations of the Estimates of the Study Sample Members for the Altruism Dimension of the Servant Leadership Dimensions

No.	Item	Arithmetic Average	Standard Deviation	Rank	Degree
1	The principal realizes that serving others is the essence of servant leadership	4.15	0.97	1	High
3	The principal encourages others to be proactive	4.07	0.86	2	High
2	The principal seeks to serve others	4.10	1.00	3	High
4	The principal puts the needs of teachers ahead of his personal needs	4.00	1.01	4	High
5	The principal service to teachers is reflected in word and deed	3.88	0.98	5	High
Total		4.04	0.98		High

Table (3) shows that the arithmetic averages in the altruistic dimension ranged between (3.88-4.15), with a high degree on all items, while the field as a whole obtained an arithmetic average of (4.04), with a high degree. In first place came item no. (1), which states: "The principle realizes that serving others is the essence of servant leadership" with an arithmetic average (4.15), with a high degree, and in last place came item no. (5), which states: "The principal's service to teachers is reflected in word and deed" with an arithmetic average (3.88) and a high degree. This is probably due to the fact that the service provided by the principal to teachers is free of charge and he believes that this service should be provided to them by virtue of his leadership position in the school, and this seems to be clear through his behavioral practices during his dealings with them so that they reflect his values and morals, and this comes in line with what he says, does and promises. Perhaps the result came in this way because the characteristic of altruism does not exist in a way that forces everyone to adhere to it morally, so that this is represented by the lack of help to others and watching over their comfort and sacrifice for them.

The loved dimension

Table 4: Arithmetic Averages and Standard Deviations of the Estimates of the Study Sample Members for the Empowerment Dimension of the Servant Leadership Dimensions

No.	Item	Arithmetic Average	Standard Deviation	Rank	Degree
15	The principal shows interest in others by encouraging them	4.13	0.99	6	High
13	The principal shows credibility when dealing with others	4.01	0.86	7	High
14	The principal is committed to what he promises teachers	4.00	0.90	8	High
12	The principal listens to everything teachers say with great interest	3.98	1.01	9	High
11	The principal works to not overburden teachers	3.86	0.99	10	High
Total		4.00	0.95		High

Table (4) shows that the arithmetic averages in the loved dimension ranged between (3.86-4.13), with a high degree on all items, while the field as a whole obtained an arithmetic average (4.00), with a high degree. In first place came item no. (15), which states: "The principal shows interest in others by encouraging them" with an arithmetic average (4.13), with a high degree, and in last place came item no. (11), which states: "The principle works not to burden teachers with responsibilities beyond their capacity" with an arithmetic average (3.86) and a high degree. This result may be attributed to the fact that the principal looks at his employees, including teachers, administrators and other workers, as permanent members of the school community, so he works to accept them to serve the school, and achieve its goals through their various types of activity, as well as the acceptance of these workers for each other in light of the positive practices issued by the director in this field, and this result may be attributed to the school principal's belief in the importance of confidence in work, whether between him and teachers, or between Teachers themselves, or between teachers and parents of students. Therefore, the principal's ability to enhance confidence in the hearts of his employees has many positive returns and facilitates the process of communication and expression of their ideas, and provides the school administration with information that may help improve the school climate.

The humility dimension

Table (5) Arithmetic Averages and Standard Deviations of the Estimates of the Study Sample Members for the humility dimension of the Servant Leadership Dimensions

No.	Item	Arithmetic Average	Standard Deviation	Rank	Degree
17	The principal is proud of the educational achievements of teachers	3.97	0.87	11	High
18	The principal consults others for additional information	3.94	0.86	12	High
20	The principal takes into account all the feedback addressed to him by the teachers	3.86	1.00	13	High
19	The principal accepts constructive criticism with the generosity of his teachers	3.81	0.98	14	High
16	The principal apologizes for every mistake he makes towards his teachers	3.78	0.93	15	High
Total		3.87	0.93		High

Table (5) shows that the arithmetic averages in the humility dimension ranged between (3.78-3.97), with a high degree on all items, while the field as a whole obtained an arithmetic average (3.87), with a high degree. In first place came item no. (17), which states: "The principle is proud of the educational achievements of teachers" with an arithmetic average of (3.97), and a high degree, and in last place came item no. (16), which states: "The principle apologizes for every mistake made by him towards his teachers" with an arithmetic average of (3.78) and a High degree. The researcher attributes this result to the fact that school principals realize the need for their teachers to feel appreciated by the school administration for the efforts they make in order to continue their achievements, in a way that contributes to achieving the school's goals, and thus achieving its success, which is attributed to them and appreciated by principals, students and the local community.

The empowerment dimension

Table (6) Arithmetic Averages and Standard Deviations of the Estimates of the Study Sample Members for the Dimension of Empowerment of the Servant Leadership Dimensions

No.	Item	Arithmetic Average	Standard Deviation	Rank	Degree
17	The principal respects the views put forward by teachers regarding school work	3.87	0.91	16	High
18	The principal provides the information the teacher needs to do his job	3.82	0.85	17	High
20	The principal helps teachers develop themselves	3.79	0.83	18	High
19	The principal gives his teachers part of the powers that allow him to make decisions about his work	3.73	0.91	19	High
16	The principal takes the opinion of his teachers regarding the vision of the school	3.68	1.03	20	High
Total		3.87	0.93		High

Table (6) shows that the arithmetic averages in the empowerment dimension ranged between (3.68-3.87), with a high degree on all items, while the field as a whole obtained an arithmetic average of (3.78), with a high degree. In first place came item no. (7), which states: "The principal respects the opinions put forward by teachers regarding school work" with an arithmetic average (3.87), with a high degree, and in last place came item no. (6), which states: "The principal takes the opinion of his teachers regarding the vision of the school" with an arithmetic average (3.68) and a high degree. This result may be attributed to the principle's desire to develop the capabilities of teachers and develop them professionally by providing them with the opportunity to exercise some administrative tasks and not monopolizing power in his hand, but rather working to delegate some teachers some powers, and this is a reflection of the director's emphasis on the importance of the human element and AsherAkah in the administrative process, in preparation To develop it to be qualified to occupy higher administrative positions in the school, and this is only achieved by empowering and delegating some powers to take the appropriate decision in the tasks entrusted to it.

Discussion of the results of the fourth question, which states: **"Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the average response of the study sample members in the degree of practice of the servant leadership dimensions among secondary school principals in Haifa District due to the variables of gender, experience and educational qualification?"**

First: Gender variable

The results showed that there were statistically significant differences attributed to the gender variable in the degree of practice of the dimensions of servant leadership among secondary school principals, and the differences came in favor of females; and the nature of each sex could be reflected in the results; some studies indicate that women by nature tend to altruism and humility with a greater difference than men. This can be explained by the fact that teachers of both sexes appreciate the practice of their principals for this type of leadership, as they notice the extent to which they have mastery in practicing their administrative and supervisory work in order to be able to manage the educational process in their schools, and their practices reflect the degree of clarity of vision, mission, general goals and strategies that have been developed.

Second: Academic Qualification Variable

The results showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the degree of practice of the dimensions of servant leadership among principles of secondary schools in Haifa district attributed to the academic qualification variable. The researcher attributes this result to the fact that teachers who hold a bachelor's degree or studies higher, aware of the most basic pedagogical principles administrative, Which states that more participation from all elements of the school community inevitably leads to an increase in the level of performance and productivity of the institution, and this requires informing school principals of the mechanisms that raise the level of this participation, and this is what most principals are aware of, highlighting their interest in teachers through smooth dealing with them and giving a good atmosphere to the relationship with them.

Third: Experience Variable

The results showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the degree of practice of the dimensions of servant leadership among principles of secondary schools in Haifa district attributable to a variable of experience, The researcher attributes this result to the existence of a consensus among teachers of all years of service on the importance of the school principal being a leader, who is expected to take the decisionCorrect opinions in different situations and in emergency situations, And to have a right visionary who estimates things properly, and anticipates events before they happen based on a decisionThe internal and external environment of the school and their analysis.

Discuss the results of the third question, which states: **"What is the level of motivation among secondary school teachers in the Haifa District?"**

Table 7: Arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the estimates of the study sample members for the paragraphs of the level of motivation of teachers

No.	Item	Arithmetic Average	Standard Deviation	Rank	Degree
17	Accomplish the tasks assigned to me by the principal with open arms	4.10	0.94	1	High
18	I will continue to work at the school under the direction of the current principal	4.07	1.10	2	High
10	My work at school brings me a sense of accomplishment	3.99	1.03	3	High
4	The principal enhances my motivation towards work when he lets me do my work independently and without interference from him except when necessary.	3.98	1.07	4	High
9	I participate with a desire in school activities	3.94	1.02	5	High
11	The principal gives me the right morale reinforcement when I do a good job.	3.91	1.12	6	High
5	The principal boosts my motivation towards work when he emphasizes teamwork	3.90	1.08	7	High
1	The principal is working to arouse my motivation towards teaching	3.84	1.06	8	High
6	The principal creates the right opportunities for my professional development	3.83	1.14	9	High
16	The principal's way of following my performance is a driver of development	3.82	1.13	10	High
2	I trust the fairness of the principal in evaluating my performance	3.80	1.13	11	High
3	The objectivity of the principal in dealing reassures me and raises my motivation to work more	3.78	1.13	12	High
13	The principal helps me solve my professional problems	3.77	1.12	13	High
14	The principal encourages me to develop new ideas that bring creativity to my work.	3.77	1.17	14	High
12	The principal encourages me to look for new alternatives to the problems I face	3.77	1.12	15	High
15	The principal contributes to highlighting my leadership qualities	3.76	1.17	16	High
7	I feel good about the principal's leadership style	3.75	1.18	17	High
8	The principal involves me in making decisions about my work	3.71	1.14	18	High
Total		3.86	0.96		High

Table (7) shows that the arithmetic averages in the level of motivation ranged between (3.71-4.10), with a high degree on all items, and the arithmetic mean of the total degree was (3.86) with a standard deviation of (3.86), and item (17), which states "I accomplish the tasks assigned to me by the principal with open arms" came in the first place with an arithmetic average of (4.10), while item (8)) which states "The principal involves me in making decisions related to my work" with an arithmetic average of (3.71) last place.

The researcher attributes this to the fact that motivation has an important role in the teacher's perseverance in accomplishing his work, and it is the main driver of his behavior, and leads to raising the morale of teachers, doubling their achievement and production, encouraging the spirit of initiative, developing the ability to creativity and innovation, achieving harmony and integration among teachers, and the leader's understanding of the feelings of his subordinates, and standing on the problems facing teachers and working to solve them, and satisfying their basic and psychological needs.

This may be due to the fact that a successful principal is a manager who is able, with his leadership and social personality traits, to build strong relationships between him and teachers, which creates a comfortable work environment free of fanaticism and tension, teachers are happy with the principal who appreciates their work and praises their efforts in raising the achievement level of students, and they also welcome the principal who involves them in making decisions related to the school as they are responsible for implementing all decisions issued and being aware of what the student needs.

Discuss the results of the fourth question, which states: "**Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the average response of the study sample members in the level of motivation of secondary school teachers in the Haifa District due to the variables of gender, experience and educational qualification?**"

First: Gender variable

The results showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the level of motivation of secondary school teachers in Haifa District due to the gender variable. This result can be explained by the fact that the gender variable does not affect the level of motivation of teachers. Motivation is an internal state that directs behavior towards satisfying a particular need, based on the type and severity of that need, and regardless of the gender of the individual. This may also be due to the fact that teachers of both sexes are more motivated to work if they feel safe and secure and have the opportunity to express their views on conflicts that arise in their schools.

Second: Academic Qualification Variable

The results showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the level of motivation among secondary school teachers in Haifa district attributed to a variable of educational qualification of teachers, which indicates that the qualifications of teachers, whatever their level or degree, are not considered an indicator of their level of motivation towards their profession.

Third: Experience variable

The results showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the level of motivation among secondary school teachers in Haifa district, attributable to a variable years of experience of teachers, which indicates that teachers with less experience and long experience in education have the same level of motivation, because the experiences they gained in their work through the qualification and training they obtained earned them the same skills, which may mean that the passage of time in the teaching profession and the increase in years of experience does not necessarily lead to an increase in the level of motivation.

Discuss the results of the fifth question, which states: **"Is there a statistically significant correlation at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the servant leadership of secondary school principals and the level of motivation of secondary school teachers in the Haifa district?"**

To answer this question, Pearson's correlation coefficients were extracted between the degree of servant leadership practice of secondary school principals and the level of motivation of teachers in Haifa District, and Table (10) shows these results:

Table 10: Pearson's Correlation Coefficients between the Servant Leadership Style of Secondary School Principals and the Level of Motivation of Teachers in the Haifa District

Dimensions of servant driving					
	Altruism	Love	modesty	Empowerment	Total degree
Motivation	**0.877	**0.911	**0.865	**0.894	**0.732

** Statistically significant at 0.01

It is clear from the previous table that all the values of Pearson's correlation coefficients between the degree of practice of secondary school principals in Haifa District of servant leadership in all its dimensions (altruism, love, humility, and empowerment), as well as the total degree of servant leadership and the level of motivation of teachers, as well as the total degree of motivation of secondary school teachers in Haifa District are positive, and a function statistically at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.01$), which shows that hereas a statistically significant positive relationship at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.01$) between the degree of practice of servant leadership by secondary school principals and the level of motivation of secondary school teachers in Haifa. This relationship can be explained by the fact that servant leadership at its core seeks to create a healthy school environment based on spreading a culture of love, humility and altruism. In light of this, this type of leadership works to meet the multiple requirements and needs of teachers, which increases their motivation to work.

Recommendations

- The need for secondary school principals in Haifa District to adopt the dimensions of servant leadership, because of its role in achieving the school's goals and motivating teachers, which will reflect positively on their motivation.
- Spreading the culture of servant leadership among all principals in their schools, and urging them to continue it.

- Providing training programs based on dialogue and discussion in the training plan for school principals, taking into account the dimensions of servant leadership, and translating them into practical and procedural steps.
- Providing greater opportunities for secondary school teachers in Haifa District in school work and their involvement in decision-making, encouraging them to put forward ideas and proposals, as well as formulating a vision and mission for the school, which contributes to increasing their motivation and commitment to their schools.
- Participation of teachers in leadership tasks, and delegate some powers to them, to perform their tasks to the fullest.
- Work on building an organizational culture in schools to increase the participation of teachers in the educational process, and to enhance their motivation to work.

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